

Isotopic exchange reactions: Part II*. Exchange of Chlorine between acetyl chloride and cadmium chloride

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The exchange of chlorine between liquid acetyl chloride and cadmium chloride, though rapid, is not complete. This is explained as due to the incomplete formation of a solid compound of the type $(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2^+$ $(\text{CdCl}_2)^-$, which acts as a protective film on the surface of cadmium chloride hindering further reaction between unreacted cadmium chloride and acetyl chloride. Complete exchange of chlorine occurs when benzyl-dimethylphenyl-ammonium chloride is added to the reaction mixture.

The present authors have reported earlier¹ that no exchange of chlorine takes place between liquid acetyl chloride and insoluble sodium chloride. Cadmium chloride, though insoluble in acetyl chloride, can react with it to form compounds which may provide a path for chlorine exchange. Attempts² to isolate solid solvates of cadmium chloride with acetyl chloride have not been successful but this may be due to the instability of the solvates under the experimental conditions employed. Chlorine exchange studies are well suited to throw light on solute-solvent interaction in the system, CdCl_2 (solid)—Acetyl chloride (liquid). The results of such studies are described in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals used were of A. R. quality and whenever necessary they were subjected to further purification. Tracer chlorine-36 in hydrochloric acid solution of specific activity of 100 micro curies per gram of chlorine was obtained from Atomic Energy Establishment, Trombay. Acetyl chloride was dried over sodium metal and labelled with chlorine-36 by exchange reaction with benzyl-dimethylphenylammonium chloride containing chlorine-36 as described below.

Dry acetyl chloride was distilled under reduced pressure into a vessel containing labelled benzyl-dimethyl-phenylammonium chloride. The reaction vessel was kept cooled with dry ice-acetone slush. The solution was stirred continuously with a magnetic stirrer and after 15-20 minutes acetyl chloride was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and collected in a dry vessel. Its specific activity was determined before use.

A.R. cadmium chloride was powdered and passed through sieves of different mesh sizes—60 (251 microns), 120 (124 microns) and 300 (50 microns). It was dried in an air oven at 120°—140°C. and prior to exchange runs further dried at 120°C. under vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide in a glass flow system.

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1. K. K. Dasai and B. C. Haldar, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 116 (Part I of this series)
2. D. Singh, S. S. Sandhu and R. C. Paul, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 315.

Silica powder was obtained by grinding pyrex glass in an agate mortar fitted to an electric grinder. It was sieved through a 300 mesh sieve and dried at 160°C. in an air oven for two hours before its use in the experiment.

TABLE I
Exchange of chlorine between acetyl chloride and cadmium chloride
Room Temperature = 27°C.

Wt. of CdCl ₂ taken in g. (300 mesh).	Wt. of AcCl taken in g.	Time of contact in hours.	Activity of AcCl before exchange c/m.	Expected activity of CdCl ₂ presuming 1:1 complex, c/m.	Observed activity of CdCl ₂ c/m.	% Exchange
*0.9730	3.60	24	557	185.3	48 ± 3	25.9 ± 1.6
**0.3459	2.044	4	588	218.1	54 ± 4	24.8 ± 1.8
0.3531	2.393	4	538	196.0	69 ± 4	35.2 ± 2.0
0.3532	2.423	4	2430	812.3	303 ± 8	37.3 ± 1.0
***0.2733	1.653	4	588	196.1	70 ± 4	35.7 ± 2.0
0.3532	2.537	0.12 to 0.50	1385	461.7	163 ± 6	35.3 ± 1.3
0.2534	4.428	4	2430	808.7	254 ± 7	31.9 ± 0.9

*60 mesh ;

**120 mesh ;

***temperature of reaction mixture varied between -30 and -40°C. during contact period.

TABLE II
Exchange of chlorine between labelled acetyl chloride and cadmium chloride in presence of benzylidimethylphenylammonium chloride.

Wt. of (300 mesh) soluble CdCl ₂ taken.	Wt. of AcCl chloride taken.	Wt. of AcCl taken	Time of contact in hrs.	Activity of AcCl, c/m.	Expected activity of CdCl ₂ for 100% exchange, c/m.	Observed activity of CdCl ₂ c/m.	% Exchange	Remarks
0.2903 g.	11.3 mg.	2.646 g.	—	1144 ± 15.5 (before exchange)	—	—	—	—
			0.25	88 ± 13.5	980 ± 11.6	299 ± 7.3	62.9 ± 3.1	Molar ratio of soluble chloride to cadmium chloride is equal to 1:34
			0.50	917 ± 13.6				
			1.00	904 ± 13.4				
			2.00	919 ± 13.6				
			23.00	911 ± 13.6				
0.3547 g.	0.5534 g.	3.324 g.	0.25	1426 ± 12.9	1442 ± 11.8	1434 ± 11.5	99.3 ± 0.8	Molar ratio of soluble chloride to cadmium chloride is equal to 1.
			0.50	1433 ± 12.8				
			2.00	1442 ± 12.8				
			24.00	1429 ± 12.7				

Benzylidimethylphenyl ammonium chloride was prepared and purified by the method described in the literature^{3,4}. Exchange runs were carried out in an all glass apparatus

3. W. Michler and A. Grandmann, *Ber.*, 1877, 10, 2079.

4. D. E. Ryan, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1956, 34, 1689.

as described in reference 1. All samples were counted with an end window G. M. counter. To study the effect of temperature, the reaction vessel was maintained between -30°C . and -40°C . (measured with a pentane thermometer) by surrounding it with a Dewar's flask containing dry ice-acetone mixture.

DISCUSSION

The results in Table I indicate that the exchange of chlorine between labelled acetyl chloride and cadmium chloride is partial, independent of contact time allowed in the present investigation and not affected by lowering the temperature of the reaction mixture to -40°C . during the contact period. The value of percentage exchange does not vary with the change in the molar ratio of acetyl chloride: cadmium chloride from 15.8 to 28.0 and the particle size of cadmium chloride from 60 to 120 mesh. However, with 300 mesh cadmium chloride an increase of 9% is observed. Addition of 1.55g. of silica to a mixture of 0.353g. of cadmium chloride and 2.423g. of acetyl chloride does not cause significant change in the value of chlorine exchange. The partial exchange of chlorine may be explained as due to the incomplete formation of a complex of the type $(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})^+(\text{CdCl}_2)^-$. The formation of the complex is not complete because the solid complex acts as a protective film on the surface of cadmium chloride, hindering further reaction between unreacted cadmium chloride and acetyl chloride. Assuming the complex as formulated above, the calculated yield on the basis of percentage of chlorine exchange is $35.1 \pm 3.2\%$ with 300 mesh cadmium chloride. It may be pointed out that Lewis and Sowerby⁵ have proposed the formation of a similar type of complex between cadmium chloride and nitrosyl chloride. Further, the existence of CdCl_2^- ions has been established by Belyear⁶ and Bloom⁷ in molten mixture of alkali chloride and cadmium chloride.

It is interesting to note that the exchange of chlorine between acetyl chloride and cadmium chloride is enhanced by the addition of inactive benzyldimethylphenyl-ammonium chloride and is complete when the molar ratio of cadmium chloride to benzyldimethylphenylammonium chloride is equal to one. The solid obtained at the end of exchange runs was separated and treated with benzene and ether to remove adsorbed acetyl chloride and then with chloroform to remove free benzyldimethylphenylammonium chloride. It was finally dried under vacuum at room temperature and analysed for cadmium and chlorine. The results of analysis show that it contains cadmium and chlorine in the ratio 1:2.8, indicating the formation of a complex of formula $[(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{CH}_2)-(\text{CH}_2)_2-\text{N}-(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)]^+ [\text{CdCl}_2]^-$ which provides the path for complete chlorine exchange observed experimentally.

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5. J. Lewis and D. Sowerby, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 150.

6. Belyear and Mironov, *Zhur. Obshchei Khim.*, 1954, 22, 734.

7. H. Bloom and Heymann R., *Proc. Roy. Soc., A*, 1947, 188, 392.